

Cognitive Dissonance Behaviour Spectered in Literature

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“A man with a conviction is a hard man to change. Tell him you disagree and he turns away. Show him facts or figures and he questions your sources.”

- Leon Festinger

Literature is always been an application of analysis for the betterment of understanding a concept. Theories are obviously applicable in many areas of literature. Theories are applied in literature to make literature practical and to cultivate in human life. The theory may be successful or unsuccessful but it achieves a role to experiment a trial. These theories also accelerate the literature to step to the next level.

Leon Festinger an American social psychologist worked on the theory of Cognitive Dissonance in 1957. He is educated psychology under Kurt Lewin, a German-American psychologist. He is a significant person experimenting social psychology. He also has his excellence in Archaeology and history. Leon Festinger is a dynamic psychologist of 20th century among B.F.Skinner, Jean Piaget, Sigmund Freud and Albert Bantura. Leon Festinger is known for Cognitive Dissonance, Effort Justification and Social Comparison theory. Cognitive Dissonance theory renders the concept of decision-making behavior in a person's life and the conflict in the mind because of various decisions. To process an action one has to take a decision, while doing so he may have an inconsistency of thoughts or ideas which results in chaos can also stated as Dissonance. This inconsistency of ideas may result in Devastation of an action; mostly this goes wrong.

Cognitive Dissonance is stated in Cambridge Business English Dictionary as

“an uncomfortable feeling that comes from believing or thinking two different things that cannot both be right. This feeling might be caused, for example, when someone wants to or has to do something that they believe to be wrong”

The analysis of this Cognitive Dissonance with the literary characters explores in the situation of each human life. Each and everyone face such a situation in their life. Here are some of the

Flavours of Literature

literary characters which take a decision with two or more ideas which leads their surroundings to wreckage are as follows: Christopher Marlowe's Dr. Faustus, William Shakespeare's Othello and Stephen King's Carrie White.

Christopher Marlowe's Dr. Faustus is a tragic play. It is a plot of a great scholar Dr. Faustus who tries to pursue Necromancy by selling his soul to Lucifer. In the instance of selling his soul he has given an option to think, the option itself given by the Lucifer. The evil angel and good angel in the play are to guide Dr. Faustus in the plot. It can be seen through the dialogues of good angel and bad angel towards Faustus.

The good angel and the evil angel can be analyzed as the two factors or thoughts of Faustus. He is guided with good advice by good angel and the bad advice by the evil angel. Even though he is having good thoughts he gave space to the bad thoughts which ends in his horrible end that his body is broken into pieces and taken by Lucifer. This clutch of thoughts is called as Cognitive Dissonance.

William Shakespeare is one of the famous dramatists of British classics. Shakespeare's Othello is one of the prolific Tragedies. His remarkable character Othello has met with this Cognitive Dissonance. Othello loves his wife Desdemona with all his heart. His growth is not tolerated by Iago, one of the extravagant villains of Shakespeare. Iago plans to destroy Othello's reputation and peace by killing his love. Iago makes plan to show Desdemona as a betrayer. Othello though loved her completely, at a circumstance of Iago's trap he believes Iago's words and killed his true and innocent beloved Desdemona. Thus, Othello's inconsistency of thoughts about Desdemona puts him in the situation of Cognitive Dissonance. This situation of Othello can be seen through his dialogues before Desdemona's death. Later he repents for his doing which can be seen his dialogue, Othello: I kiss'd thee ere I kill'd thee; no way but this, Killing myself to die upon a kiss. (Act V, Scene II)

Stephen King's character Carrie White from Carrie too destroys her life because of chaos thoughts. Carrie White is a Teenager brought up in an Orthodox Christian family and she has lots of dream as a teenager. Her mother Margaret never allowed her to enjoy the Teenage stuff because she believes in Old Testament and strong religious doctrines. Carrie can change her mind to follow one belief but she end-up in dilemma because of Dissonance. In an instance, Carrie's situation turns awful that she cannot balance her family and the society. The family and society puts pressure towards her deliberately, that she cannot handle it. She outraged and burst into a beast and kills everyone through her Telekinesis power. As a pure soul she may have dissonant cognition while killing everyone thus she may have an discrepancy of thoughts which escort to ruin her life.

Cognitive Dissonance also reflects in many literary works. In Aldous Huxley's The Brave New World, John suffers in Dissonance. Chinua Achebe's Things Fall Apart Okonkwo suffers a kind of Dissonance as they reach the ultimate tragic-end. Thus, in literature too the characters, especially the protagonists undergo such an uncomfortable situation, such situation can make a great change or twist in the story. Dissonance of inconsistency in thoughts can be managed through many techniques.

There are some techniques to come out of Cognitive Dissonance; it is described in the above lines. A person when taking a decision shouldn't allow dissonant beliefs to occur or to change their own beliefs and try new beliefs or thoughts can make the situation even better. The cause of allowing Dissonant Beliefs may kill the humanism in the world and the world will become appallingly evil.

The study of Cognitive Dissonance helps a person to make decisions without absurdity and to solve the problems easily in critical situations. Literature explores the reality of life and illuminates the way to attain wisdom more than knowledge. The characters in Literature can be phenomenal

Flavours of Literature

that it can be an example to live alike or to be aware. A literary theory leads us to experiment our life in a trial which will be always a constant learning.

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